

E-Marketing of Agricultural Products

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ABSTRACT

The internet has changed the world. In line with other sectors, retail business have taken up e-marketing or internet marketing, expanding outreach to customers beyond their conventional shopping places. Farmers can use internet on many possible ways to sell their products. Using internet as a way of selling agricultural products is changing marketing channels in the agribusiness industry.

Now farmers will be able to sell their produce through e-market platform i.e. the National Agriculture Market (NAM) which was launched by our Prime Minister Narendra Modi.

Agricultural markets are characterized by poor competitiveness, fragmentation, inefficiency, presence of executive middlemen and frequent price manipulations. E-Marketing of Agricultural Products is an electronic trading portal for agricultural products through which many of the farmer's problems will be solved. This paper analysis the nature and importance of e-marketing of agricultural Products.

KEYWORDS: *E-marketing, Agriculture, Agricultural products, Farmers, Internet and Technology.*

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is the backbone of India. More than 60% of Indian workers are involved in Agriculture. Agriculture refer to the cultivation of land and breeding of animals and plants to provide food, fiber, medicinal plants and other products to sustain and enhance life. Agriculture was the key development in the rise of sedentary human civilization, whereby farming of domesticated species created food surpluses that enabled people to live in cities.

Agricultural products refer to crops, livestock and livestock products including field crops, fruits, vegetables. Horticulture specialties, Cattle, sheep, pigs, goats, horses, Donkeys, poultry, fur-bearing animals, milk, Eggs, aquaculture and furs. More than one third of the world's workers are employed in agriculture. After agriculture second only to the service sector but over the past several years the number of agricultural workers in developed countries have decreased significantly.

E-marketing is referred to those strategies and techniques which use online ways to reach target customers. E-Marketing is also known as Internet Marketing, Web Marketing, Digital Marketing, or Online Marketing. E-marketing is the process of marketing a product or service using the Internet. E-marketing not only includes marketing on the Internet, but also includes marketing through e-mail and wireless media. E-marketing of agricultural products means marketing of agricultural products through online ways from agricultural producers to any business houses or ultimate consumers.

Agricultural producers are also trying to develop this marketing channel even though there are many barriers of selling agricultural products via the Internet. Farmers may use the Internet to sell agricultural products for consumers and also for organizations. E-marketing is most useful to the farmers since the benefits are high and electronic systems are ready to serve customers all over the world and open for 24 hours in a day. The cost incurring is also low.

Agriculture is the basement for any country for their continuous development and survival. So, agricultural development is the utmost priority now as role of digital marketing is concerned, it tries to expand the reach of the people associated with agriculture, it helps in promoting right agri products to its rightful buyers by reaching out to new people across diverse locations.

Benefits of E-Marketing to Farmers

- **Wide market:-** Farmers can sell their products worldwide. It covers large number of customers of different states and different countries also.
- **Open for 24 hours/continuous market:-** online market is opened for 24 hours in a day so, farmers can sell their products at any time as and when they wish to sell.
- **Right person and Right price:** farmers have to place their products through online. If they get proper price for their products then only they have to sell their products to the right person.
- **Less cost:** There is no middlemen so there is a less cost or sometimes free of cost.
- **No waste of agricultural products;** Sometimes most of the agriculture products will be destroyed because of non availability of customers on time. Since online market is a continuous market there is no problem of wastage of any products.

5 Ways to Sell Agricultural Products Online

1. Online Market Place:

As there is a physical market place for agricultural products, there is also online market place for it. With the proliferation of online market places, selling agricultural products online just got a lot easier. There are many online market places in India for farmers. Some examples are Kisan market, Farmers online market etc. Listing your farm products on these platforms is another way to get more exposure, and subsequently sales.

The first thing to do if you want to sell your agricultural products on an online market place is to read their terms & conditions. These would usually contain their charges and general rules and regulations. You wouldn't want to get kicked off the online market place because you violated their terms whether knowingly or unknowingly

2. Online Grocery Store:

Online groceries stores are a good place to sell off some of your agricultural products. According

to wikipedia, "A *grocery store is a retail store that primarily sells food*". While the food items online grocery stores sell may differ per store, if you're a farmer that probably grows agricultural products like potatoes, poultry product (e.g chickens & turkeys), aquatic animals (e.g fishery products), and a couple of other farm products. Big basket founded in 2011 (online super market in india is one of the examples for Online grocers. many online grocery stores would be a good fit for you.

3. Social Media:

Recently Social Media is playing vital role in marketing. The success of Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and many other social networks has helped many small business owners to reach large number of customers without leaving their computer screens. Social media marketing is growing stronger day by day, and is capable to either explode your sales, or destroy it.

4. Personal Web Store:

owning your own web store is the best online way to sell your agricultural products as compared to selling your agricultural products on social media, an online grocery store, and an online market place, because having personal web store enables you to closely control your farm products sales on your platform, in case you get kicked off the rest.

5. Online Food Delivery:

By processing agricultural products to edible form, they can be sold online via a food delivery service. There are many restaurants that deliver food to customers when customers order food online. The food delivery is usually done via online food shopping sites like Hello Food, Food Panda, etc.

Platforms for E-marketing of Agricultural products in India

KisanMandi.com

It is the online Agricultural Market where you can Buy or Sell or Advertise fruits & vegetables, agri produce or any agri machinery or Tools or Tractors etc. it will really fulfil our dream "Sabko Sahi Mol".

Kisanmandi Online Agri Market Private Limited is incorporated/ registered as a Private Limited Company on 26-04-2016, is recognized as a startup by the Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion, Govt. of India.

It has three verticals as under:

Retail – B2C: Online Vegetable store in Main cities of India.

Online wholesale – B2B: it is a Online Portal here farmers can submit their Agricultural Products for Sale.

Vendors (Channel Partners) – It is a Online Portal here Manufacturers or Big Distributors can sell Agri Machinery and products, Packing and food storage Materials to the Farmers.

Also, Kisanmandi.com will be catering to almost all the needs of the agriculture fraternity where they will find all commodities/ items ranging from Tractors. Diesel Engines, Pump Sets, Agro Farm Implements, Cattle feed, seeds, Grain storage bins, Water Tankers, Wheel Barrows, Trolleys, Tree Guards and Gardening tools etc.

National Agriculture Market or eNAM

It is one of the good online trading platforms for agricultural commodities in India. This market helps farmers, traders and buyers for online trading in commodities. This market helps to discover better price for the products and smooth marketing of agricultural products. The market transactions stood at ₹36,200 crores by January 2018, mostly intra-market. More than 90 commodities including staple food grains, vegetables and fruits are currently listed in its list of commodities available for trade. The eNAM markets are proving their greatness as it is witnessed with some aspects like the crops are weighed immediately and the stock is lifted on the same day and the payments are cleared online. In February 2018, some attractive features like MIS dashboard, BHIM and other mobile payments, enhanced features on the mobile app such as gate entry and payment through mobile phones and farmers database is helping adoption even more. The present trading is done mostly for intra-market, but in phases, it will be rolled out to trade in inter-market, inter-state, creating a unified national market for agricultural commodities.

It was launched by Ministry of Agriculture, Government of India. The electronic market pilot across India was launched on 14 April 2016 by Prime Minister of India, Narendra Modi. The Portal is managed by Small Farmers’ Agribusiness Consortium (SFAC) with technology provider, NFCL’s iKisan division. A similar project was

initiated by the Congress government in Karnataka, during UPA period and it had been a great success. NDA government has rolled it out nationally.

eNAM platform facilitates farmers to trade directly on their own through mobile app or through registered commission agents.

The eNAM is linked with 585 markets (APMCs) in 16 states and 2 union territory. 45 lakh farmers got membership in 15 states. This market is facilitating traders and exporters in acquiring quality produce in bulk, at one place and it will ensure transparent financial transactions.

The Government plans to connect over 22,000 GrAMs, local farmers markets, with the platform.

Agricultural Marketing Information Network (AGMARKNET)

It was launched by the Union Ministry of Agriculture in March 2000. The Directorate of Marketing and Inspection (DMI), under the Ministry, links around 7,000 agricultural wholesale markets in India with the State Agricultural Marketing Boards and Directorates for effective information exchange. This e-governance portal AGMARKNET, implemented by National Informatics Centre (NIC), facilitates generation and transmission of prices, commodity arrival information from agricultural produce markets, and web-based dissemination to producers, consumers, traders, and policy makers transparently and quickly.

The AGMARKNET website (<http://www.agmarknet.nic.in>) is a G2C e-governance portal that caters to the needs of various stakeholders such as farmers, industrialists, policy makers and academic institutions by providing agricultural marketing related information from a single window.

Challenges for E-marketing of agricultural products

1. Lack of knowledge of Electronic medias
Majority of the farmers do not have computer knowledge and unable to operate Android mobiles so may difficult them to go with e-marketing of agricultural products.

2. Worldwide competition
There are many number of sellers from different geographical areas of different countries. So it is

difficult to expect sell of our products with right price and right time.

3. No security:

Sometimes farmers may enter fake websites or fake online portals. This will be wastage of time and products.

4. Cannot fully depend on E-marketing.

Because still many number of customers prefer to purchase the products physically. So it is necessary to depends on offline market also.

Conclusion

Traditional marketing for agriculture products suffering from many drawbacks. Introduction of E-Platform for agricultural products is helpful from the point of farmers as well as governments. In this process every citizen of the country should support to the farmers. Development of nation depends upon development of farmers because farmer is the backbone of the country. By giving online marketing education to farmers, farmers will get marketing opportunity to their products that will contribute lot to the development of the nation.

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